

AMR in Poultry Birds: A Public Health Threat

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Antimicrobial resistance is a global health threat, and widespread use of antibiotics in animal health is one of its contributing sources. Poultry meat one of the most consumed meats throughout the world and for production of poultry meat, poultry birds raised under intensive and semi-intensive conditions in which high amount of antibiotics used to treat animals or as a growth promoter. Unfortunately, the exponential use and misuse of these antibiotics has led to the development and dissemination of antimicrobial drug resistance, which is currently a serious public health concern. Multidrug-resistant bacteria are on the rise, being responsible for serious infections in humans and animals. According to OIE (world organization for animal health) 3500-5000 tons of antibiotics used for human therapy and 50,000 tons of antibiotics used in animals.

AMR (Antimicrobial resistance) in poultry birds is not only affect poultry bird health, but also be a source of resistant bacteria (including zoonotic bacteria) that may also represent a risk to human health. Furthermore, the emergence of multidrug resistance (MDR) has made the treatment of infections challenging. If MDR is not addressed, it is estimated to cause many deaths and lead to the next pandemic.

According to a report of science advisor, AMR in animals has increased by 50% in the past two decades against a typical approval cycle of new antibiotics which could be about several years (Thomas *et al.*, 2019).

Introduction:

In the past four decades, the Indian poultry industry has seen a paradigm shift as it has moved from mere backyard activities into major commercial ventures. It is one of the fastest-

growing segments of the agriculture sector in India today. India is one of the biggest poultry meat consumers and AMR is a worldwide health concern due to continuously increasing human populations and rendering food security. According to the FAO, in 2020, the poultry meat represented almost 40% of global meat production (FAO; 2020).

Antibiotics have been used in animal production for over fifty years as therapeutic and prophylactic agents or as growth promoters. The efficacy and cost-effectiveness of the majority of these antibiotics led to their indiscriminate usage. Consequently, the misuse and overuse of these antimicrobials promoted the establishment of microbial reservoirs carrying

AMR determinants in livestock, including poultry (Marshall *et al.*, 2011). As some of the antimicrobials applied to animals are the same as those administered to humans, AMR dissemination poses a serious threat to the effective treatment of serious bacterial infections in humans, leading to higher medical costs, prolonged hospital stays and increased mortality.

Antimicrobial resistance has led to the emergence of so-called “superbugs”, which are challenging to health care workers, veterinarians, and other animal health providers due to a reduction of effective therapeutic options to prevent, control, and treat infectious diseases. Animals and humans are becoming helpless, once again, in the face of infection.

AMR Current scenario:

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), India has among the highest bacterial disease burden in the world. Antibiotics, therefore, have a critical role in limiting death and disease in the country. The progress of AMR is a major global

concern and if not addressed, could lead to a world in which the antibiotics which we use in human healthcare would no longer be effective, thus, taking us back to an age in which people died from simple infections. AMR is of particular concern in developing nations, including India, where the burden of infectious disease is high and healthcare spending is low. However, the unreasonable use of antibiotics has risen to development of resistant bacteria that may lead to the transfer of resistant bacteria and its resistant factors from animals to humans. Non-therapeutic antimicrobial uses are also linked to the propagation of multidrug resistance (MDR), including resistance against drugs that were never used on the farm.

Due to this concern, Sweden firstly prohibited the use of some of the antibiotics in animal feeds in 1986 and European Union (EU) member nations banned all antibiotic growth promoters in 2006 according to European Parliament and Council Regulation EC No. 1831/2003 (Van *et al.*, 2015). Following the Global Action Plan on AMR launched in 2015, India's National Action Plan (NAP) for AMR was released in April 2017 by the Union Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. The first of six strategic priorities outlined in the NAP is to improve awareness and understanding of AMR through effective communication, education and training at ground level. Kerala became the first state to adopt the sub national State Action Plan in October 2018 (Ranjalkar *et al.*, 2019).

India has also launched the 'National programme on the containment of antimicrobial resistance' under the aegis of the National Centre for Disease Control (NCDC). The objectives of this programme are to establish a laboratory-based AMR surveillance system of 30 network laboratories, generating quality data on AMR for pathogens of public health importance; to strengthen infection control guidelines and practices, and promote rational use of antibiotics; and to generate awareness about the use of antibiotics in both healthcare providers and in the community.

Reason Antimicrobial Drug Resistance in Poultry Production

- Poultry feeds available to the farmers are unregulated and unlabeled.

- Self-medication through hearsay or information gathered from the internet or upon the advice of the shop-keeper.
- Non-availability and non-utilization of the laboratory service for cultures and antibiotic susceptibility testing.
- Varying approach of treating doctors – owing to the anxiety of missing a bacterial infection or covering for secondary bacterial infection, lack of up-to-date knowledge on the current revised guidelines and algorithms for antibiotic usage.
- Empirical but incorrect use of antibiotics, simultaneous use of more than a single antibiotic when actually not necessary, not de-escalating when possible, inefficiency in the review of the response to antibiotics.
- Regulatory issues – Lack of strict implementation of policies (such as schedule H1) and control by the regulatory authorities.
- Varied perceptions such as perceived demand and expectations among key stakeholders and ethical challenges among healthcare professionals.
- Unethical commercial practices to promote the sale of antibiotics in large quantities.
- Farmers were largely unaware of the risk related to AMR, the withdrawal period and the guidelines provided by the pollution control board concerning poultry establishment.
- Critically Important Antimicrobials promoted for growth promotion were found in online retail shops, despite the recommendations and regulations against them, e.g. Tylosin.
- Colistin, banned for use in animals in 2018, is still being sold as a growth promoter in online retail shops for animal products.
- Use of antibiotics by other non-medical and informal healthcare providers.

Strategies to Reduce AMR in Poultry Production:

- Improve awareness and understanding of AMR through effective communication, education, and training.
- Strengthen knowledge and evidence through surveillance.

- Reduce the incidence of infection through effective infection, prevention and control.
- Optimize the use of antimicrobial agents in all sectors.
- Promote investments for AMR activities, research, and innovations.
- Strengthen India's leadership on AMR by means of collaborations on AMR at international, national, and sub-national levels.
- One of the main objectives of the global action proposed by the WHO in 2015 is the reduction in infection incidence via effective sanitation and the application of hygiene and infection preventive measures.
- Due to the emergence of resistant microorganisms, research has focused on finding strategies alternative to conventional antibiotics, such as antimicrobial peptides, bacteriophages, probiotics and nanoparticles, as well as the use of alternative treatments.
- Given proper vaccine as per the schedule recommended by the government guideline.

Conclusion:

Antimicrobial resistance is a common problem that all the countries of the world are facing right now, be it a developed country or a developing country. The continuous and rapid emergence of antibiotic-resistant pathogens has severely affected the country's medical systems and if stringent policies are not implemented, the pathogens that are resistant to antibiotics, especially multidrug-resistant bacteria, which are also known as 'superbugs' may cause harm to such an extent that the antibiotics will fail to treat the minutest of infections.

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